

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL CHANGES ON THE VOCABULARY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The present article is dedicated to the analysis of the influence of socio-political factors in the historical development of the English language of the word stock of this language.

Key words: Social factors, Historical development, Language, England, Christianity, 6th-7th century AD, English vocabulary, Latin influence, Old English vocabulary, Religious domain, Borrowed words, Greek, Globalization, Oxford Dictionary, Old English, Middle English, Apostol, Apostle, Apostolus, Apostolos, Anthem, Antiphona, Devil, Diabolus, Diabo

Social factors, like other factors, occupy an important place in the historical development of any language. For instance, among the most important social changes in the history of England, one can show the introduction of Christianity in the late 6th-7th century AD. As a result, the English vocabulary was enriched to a great extent with words of such a type. In this regard, we can also note the greatest influence of Latin on the composition of Old English Vocabulary, greatest part of which were largely religious domain words. The new religion introduced many new notions requiring new names; most of the latter were words borrowed from Latin or Greek through Latin. This problem is becoming very actual during the last decades in terms of globalization process [1; 2; 3].

We can select the following words of this type from Oxford Dictionary as an example:

Old English	Middle English	Latin	Greek
apostol	apostle	apostolus	apostolos
antefh	anthem	antiphona	antiphona
deofol	devil	diabolus	diabolos
mumic	monk	monachus	monachos

From the same source, many more examples can be found that are characteristic of modern English: *pope, psalm, temple*.

In the 7th century AD, Christianity spread throughout England. As a result of new contacts with Rome, Latin was introduced into England as the language of the church. As a result of such contacts with Romano-Latin culture, we can cite the penetration of Latin words, mainly Greek ones, associated with religious and ecclesiastical concepts into English, and a significant increase in the amount of acquisitions during the Roman occupation. It should be noted that during the Christianization period, no English word went out of circulation and was not subject to the influence of semantic processes [7, p.21].

Most of the words originally borrowed from this type of Latin later disappeared again or were replaced by the corresponding French forms. For example, according to Kotsiol, modern English word *sign* was like *seʒn* in Old English [5, p. 13].

The range of concepts and ideas that spread after the introduction of Christianity is considered to be many words related to science, along with elements of Greek-Latin culture. For example, the Old English *fers* can be traced back to the word *versus* – poem in Latin. During the period of Christianization, words related to the school were also borrowed. For example, like *scol* – school and *maʒister* – teacher.

In the early New English period, in connection with the formation of the nation, a more conscious attitude towards the national language was formed, the national language began to be consciously processed, its literary norms were stabilized. English begun to grow from the status of the language used daily to become a more literary language. In this regard, introduction of printing by W. Caxton in 1475 was of great importance in the process of forming certain language norms [4, p.19]. Books published in English literary language and distributed throughout the country in the late XV century, and as a result stimulated the growth of dictionary content. Thus, there was a strong impetus for the spread of a single literary language. With its help, certain forms of this language were tightened and language norms have been strengthened.

In the late 18th century there began an Industrial Revolution and the development of the field, which began in connection with the invention of steam machinery by the D. Watt and supplemented the English vocabulary content with terms related to textiles and other fields. As a result of the development of science and technology in the 19th century, as well as scientific and technical revolutions in the 20th century, the English language word stock was enriched to a great extent [6, p. 211].

It should be noted that the specific conditions for the development of the English word stock prove that a certain part of it consists of borrowed words (in addition to the above-mentioned ones, we can also cite terms related to the maritime and trade sphere as an example). In addition to the Norman and Scandinavian invasions, Christianization and the invention of printing, external factors such as the Great 100 years War between England and France, which provided a certain amount of borrowed words from French. At the same time the growth of the English-speaking middle class, factors such as the strengthening of England's role as a powerful state, the expansion of the British Empire also served as important factors in the process of enriching English language word stock.

Based on the above given materials, we can conclude that under the influence of major political and social changes that have occurred throughout the history of English society, the word stock of the English literary language had been significantly enriched with words borrowed from French, Scandinavian and Latin, as well as from other languages. In this, we are guided by the influence of external

factors on the composition of the dictionary of English within the framework of the sociolinguistic framework “society-civilization-language”.

It should be noted that such external factors of the language as political and social changes directly affect the formation and development of the word stock of the English language[8; 1194-1198].

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